

METHODS OF ENDOVIDEOLAPAROSCOPIC TREATMENT OF
INGUINAL AND INGUINAL HERNIAS IN CHILDREN.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7538487>

ELSEVIER

Berdiyev E.A
Abdusamatov B.Z
Usmanov X.S
Fayzullayev T.S
Republic Children's Scientific and Practical Center of Minimally Invasive and
Endovisual Surgery
Tashkent Medical Academy. Tashkent, Uzbekistan.
E-mail: ergashdh@mail.ru

Abstract: In the article, 60 children diagnosed with inguinal and inguinal hernias were treated at the Republic Children's Scientific Practical Center of Minimally Invasive and Endovisual Surgery from 2018 to 2022. The advantages of modern endolaparoscopy technologies, the time spent on the operation and the number of recurrences of hernias are low compared to the method.

Keywords: inguinal hernias, inguinal hernias, hernioplasty, children, laparoscopy

Received: 14-01-2023

Accepted: 15-01-2023

Published: 22-01-2023

About: FARS Publishers has been established with the aim of spreading quality scientific information to the research community throughout the universe. Open Access process eliminates the barriers associated with the older publication models, thus matching up with the rapidity of the twenty-first century.

Relevance of the problem: The problem of surgical treatment of external hernias in children remains relevant to this day and is far from a final solution. This is evidenced by the large number of surgical methods (more than 400) in the treatment of hernias in children, none of which protects the patient from recurrence of the hernia in the postoperative period. According to different authors, the number of complications after open hernioplasty (hernia recurrence, suppuration of the surgical wound, damage to the male reproductive tract, etc.) reaches 5-7%, and repeated interventions reach 30% or more. Modern endoscopic technologies have allowed radical changes in the surgical correction of this disease.

The purpose of the work is to treat hernias in children with minimally invasive methods and evaluate their experience.

Materials and methods: 60 children diagnosed with invaginal hernias were treated at the Republic Children's Scientific Practical Center of Minimally Invasive and Endovisual Surgery from 2018 to 2021.

Table №1

gender	age			total
	month 1 y.o	1-3 y.o	4-7y.o	
boys	8	24	11	43
girls	3	11	3	17
total	11	35	14	60

All patients were scheduled for surgery under general anesthesia after a regular examination by a pediatrician, an anesthesiologist, complete blood, urine, blood biochemistry, blood group, HbSAg examinations. Surgery was carried out using "Karl Ztorz" (Germany) endosurgical technologies.

Results: 62 operations were performed on 60 children. 43 of them are boys and 17 are girls. Of these, 38 (63.3%) had a right-sided invaginal hernia, 20 (33.4%) had a left-sided hernia, and 2 (3.3%) had a bilateral hernia. 35 children underwent endovideolaparoscopic hernioplasty surgery. 25 of them underwent traditional surgery. The average time of performing endovideolaparoscopic hernioplasty was 26.4-12.0 minutes, while the traditional open operation was 31.5-16.6 minutes (R-0.01).

The average hospital stay after endolaparoscopic treatment was 4.7 + 1.2 days, and after the open traditional method was 4.9 + 1.5 days. There were no complications after surgery. In only 1 patient who underwent open traditional method, a rough kelloated scar was observed in the area of the postoperative wound, the patient was prescribed scheduled physiotherapeutic treatments.

Conclusion: Endovideolaparoscopic hernioplasty has advantages in terms of criteria such as the time spent on surgery and the number of recurrences compared to conventional treatment, which allows us to consider this intervention as the method of choice in the treatment of invaginal hernia in children.

REFERENCES:

1. Pritula V.P., Rybalchenko I.G. Diagnosis and treatment of inguinal-scrotal hernias in newborns. *Pathology*. 2015;(2):48-51. [Prytula V. P, Rybalchenko I. G. Diagnosis and treatment of inguinalscrotal hernias in infants. *pathology*. 2015;(2):48-51 (in Ukraine)].
2. Lapshin V.I., Razin M.P., Smirnov A.V., Baturov M.A. Congenital direct inguinal hernia in a child. *Children's surgery*. 2017;21(1):52-53. [Lapshin V. I, Razin M. P, Smirnov A. V, Baturov M. A. Congenital direct inguinal hernia in a child. *Detskaya Khirurgiya=Russian Journal of Pediatric Surgery*. 2017;21(1):52-53 (in Russ.)]. DOI: 10.18821/1560-9510-2017-21-1-52-53.
6. Chan Y. Y, Durbin-Johnson B, Kurzrock E. A. Pediatric inguinal and scrotal surgery - Practice patterns in U.S. academic centers. *J Pediatric Surg*. 2016;51(11):1786-1790. DOI: 10.1016/j.jpedsurg. 2016.07.019.
3. Viktorov V. V., Yuldashev M. T., Alyangin V. G., Salimgareev A. A., Akbashev R. N., Makushin A. A., Sadretdinov M. M. Endosurgical treatment of strangulated inguinal and inguinal-scrotal hernia in children. Patent 2253377 Russian Federation dated 10.06.2005. [Viktorov V. V, Uldashev M. T, Alyangin V.

G, Salimgareev A. A, Akbashev R. N, Sadretdinov M. M. Method for endosurgical treatment of incarcerated inguinal hernias and hernioscrotal hernias in children. Russian Federation patent 2253377. 2005 June 10 (in Russ.)].

4. Lobe T. E, Schropp K. P. Inguinal hernias in pediatrics: initial experience with laparoscopic inguinal exploration of the asymptomatic contralateral side. *J Laparoendosc Surg.* 1992;2(3):135-40. PMID: 1535806. 12. Lee Y, Liang J. Experience with 450 cases of microlaparoscopic herniotomy in infants and children. *Pediatr Endosurg Innov Tech.* 2002;6(1):25-8. DOI: 10.1089/10926410252832410.

5. Schier F, Montupet P, Esposito C. Laparoscopic inguinal herniorrhaphy in children: a threecenter experience with 933 repairs. *J Pediatric Surg.* 2002;37(3):395-7. PMID:11877655.

6. Abd-Alrazek M, Alsherbiny H, Mahfouz M, Alsamahy O, Shalaby R, Shams A, et al. Laparoscopic pediatric inguinal hernia repair: a controlled randomized study. *J Pediatric Surg.* 2017. [Epub ahead of print]. DOI: 10.1016/j.jpedsurg.2017.07.003